

The Information about the Jama Masjid Kalai-Azizon in the Neighbourhood of Kalai Azizon in Kyzyltepo District

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Abstract:

Social and normative relations in all spheres of life of the residents of the Bukhara Emirate were strongly influenced by Islam and Sharia, which is its basis. The traditions, values, rituals, and holidays that have been preserved from centuries to centuries, have further strengthened loyalty to the traditions that have been preserved as an integral part of the people's lifestyle. In particular, the mass performance of religious ceremonies is considered to be a common characteristic of Islamic holidays with other traditions. In the Emirate of Bukhara, which is one of the major centers of Islam, there are centers of enlightenment, such as Bukhara and Samarkand, where there are places of education and the number of students was also quite large. A foreigner in Central Asia according to tourists and ambassadors, in the medieval Uzbek khanates Muslim education system is very well established, especially in Bukhara The emirate is considered one of the centers of Islamic enlightenment and the implementation of radical reforms National Revival, Spiritual Update, the National Idea, History in addressing functions of members of united society with strength The role of the science is growing. Inspection of the laws of historical development of Uzbekistan, for centuries, statehood, economic.

Research of the history of cultural process policies from a new methodological point of view Issues such as making are placed. To date, in the field of history in the field of history, there are some issues in the history of the Uzbek statehood, which is of great importance. Indeed, during the Uzbek khanite Khanity, the Islamic religion and purity, humanity and purity, the conveyance of Islam is inaccurate in the delivery of itself to generations and axity had. It is noteworthy that Islam's norms played an important role in the cultural and spiritual life of the khalmic life. Uzbekistan includes research, which is created during the independence of Uzbekistan. During this period, a wide range

of opportunities has been created for the history of our Motherland to study objectively and fairly. It is obedient to the bilateral in the time of the dictatorial system. During this period, scientific work created on the history of Uzbekistan on the basis of a new approach. H. Ziyoev, D. Alimova, Sh. Vahidov, F. Kasimov, Q. Rajabov, F. The research of certain aspects of the history of the Emirates of the Bukhara Emirate was discussed in research. The "Qal'ayi-Azizon Jame Mosque" complex is a monument located in the Qal'ayi-Azizon neighborhood of the Kyziltepa district of the Navoi region of Uzbekistan (it is described in many sources as the 18th century, but in fact it was built in the 17th-16th centuries). The minaret standing in front of the mosque is 32 meters high and is considered the tallest and most elegant of the 16th century structures of this type preserved in Central Asia. Newly reconstructed in 2021. The size of the newly built mosque is 30*12 meters, the size of the old building is 10*10 meters and the height is 6 meters. Some researchers believe that "Qal'ayi-Azizon Jame Mosque" was the first Hazrat Muhammad Abul Qasim who came to Toshabat region in the 16th century, and it was this person who caused the construction of the mosque is said to have been built by, others say that the tower in the complex dates back to the 18th century. Social and normative relations in all spheres of life of the residents of the Bukhara Emirate were strongly influenced by Islam and Sharia, which is its basis. The traditions, values, rituals, and holidays that have been preserved from centuries to centuries, have further strengthened loyalty to the traditions that have been preserved as an integral part of the people's lifestyle. In particular, the mass performance of religious ceremonies is considered to be a common characteristic of Islamic holidays with other traditions. In the Emirate of Bukhara, which is one of the major centers of Islam, there are centers of enlightenment, such as Bukhara and Samarkand, where there are places of education and the number of students was also quite large. A foreigner in Central Asia according to tourists and ambassadors, in the medieval Uzbek khanates Muslim education system is very well established, especially in Bukhara The emirate is considered one of the centers of Islamic enlightenment.

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